

Detecting, Linking, and Extracting Turkish Labor Action Events from News Articles

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Abstract

This paper presents a three stage pipeline for constructing event level data on labor actions, specifically workplace related actions in Turkey from national news coverage. The corpus utilized contains 19,886 articles published by the labor-oriented newspapers Evrensel, BirGün, and Sendika.org between the years 2023 and 2025. The three stages are as such: a title aware BERTurk classifier is used to detect labor action articles, a multilingual sentence-embedding and rule-based linker is used to group articles referring to the same event, and finally a large language model (LLM) converts multi-article clusters into structured event level records of labor activity containing specific properties of events such as outcome and industry, adapted from the coding methodology of the Labor Studies Collective (LSC) operating in Turkey. The labor action detector performs strongly in five-fold out-of-fold evaluation; achieving 0.939 precision, 0.902 recall, and 0.920 F1 on 1,407 labeled articles. Linking remains the central bottleneck. The selected configuration reached 0.613 pairwise F1 during grid selection, but only 0.230 when re-evaluated on the final dataset containing all the predicted labor events; the following clustering also generated one implausible cluster of 1,275 articles. The extraction stage produced records for 218 multi-article clusters. A manual validation of 70 randomly selected clusters, which represents 32.1 percent of the extracted set, produced an average cluster-level accuracy of 0.661 across all extracted categories. Accuracy was particularly high for the categories of union presence (0.921), employment type (0.914), location (0.877), action reason (0.857), and start date (0.829), but low for outcome (0.574), end date (0.382), and worker counts (0.269–0.366). The results show that automated detection can already reduce the labor of finding relevant articles, while event linking and several extraction fields still require direct human supervision.

Keywords: labor action; strikes; event extraction; event coreference; BERTurk; large language models; Turkish news; strike detection

1 Introduction

Quantitative research on labor activity has traditionally depended on official statistics. This source is useful in its own regard, but has its drawbacks. The main limitation of official statistics is that it cannot capture labor actions either not recorded by government officials or not recognized; resulting in missing out on labor actions where state entities cannot afford to keep track of and actions not officially recognized by labor laws and administrative procedures. This problem of reliable measurement has plagued comparative strike research for some time (Franzosi, 1989), including research on the institutional determinants and impacts of industrial conflict (Korpi & Shalev, 1979; DiNardo & Hallock, 2002; Brandl & Traxler, 2010). News based collections on the other hand can capture unofficial work stoppages, workplace occupations, illegal strikes, simple protests in the workplace, persistent resistances, and other actions that never become legal strikes. In Turkey this distinction is especially crucial since a large part of labor conflict takes place outside the scope of the narrow legal category of a strike characterized by Turkish labor legislation. Newspaper coverage also helps account for labor actions potentially overseen by officials. However, constructing such a collection of labor actions through newspaper coverage by hand is highly labor intensive and requires a vast amount of resources. This is where the need for a more efficient, semi-automated pipeline of data construction comes in.

The practical problems regarding the construction of such a pipeline are multifold. A usable event database requires tackling three separate areas of interest. First, the pipeline must detect efficiently whether an article concerns a relevant labor action. Second, it must determine whether distinct articles describe the same continuing event, since labor actions are more often than not events taking over some time and are reported on multiple times both in one newspaper and across newspapers. Third, it must extract reliable event attributes from the clustered articles for the categories of interest. This framing is shown in the broader development of automated socio-political event extraction, where document detection, event representation, and cross-document coreference are treated as connected but separately evaluated problems (Hürriyetöğlü et al., 2020; Hürriyetöğlü et al., 2021a; Hürriyetöğlü et al., 2021b; Hürriyetöğlü et al., 2022). These stages depend on one another as the performance of each stage affects the subsequent stage, making failure detrimental to the following stages. A detector can retrieve most relevant articles and still pass many irrelevant cases forward, affecting clustering performance. A linker may fail in two ways: first by keeping clusters pure by splitting one event into many fragments, and second by increasing recall by accidentally merging unrelated events together. Either of these failures, especially the second one, affects event extraction greatly.

This paper does not claim to have constructed a pipeline achieving all these goals perfectly. Instead, it should be read as a pilot study on how such a pipeline can be constructed. The contribution here is therefore humble. The paper aims to identify which parts of Turkish labor action event coding can be automated now, which parts can be semi-automated with a human in the loop configuration and which parts are subject to further research.

2 Background and the Scope of Measurement

2.1 Labor action event visibility in news data

It is true that newspaper data excel at widening the empirical field beyond legally recognized strikes. However, it does not provide a neutral window onto labor actions as a whole. To be reported on, events must first become newsworthy and then be reported on through the publication routines and political positions of a newspaper agency. Smaller workplaces, geographically distant disputes, events not in line with the interests of the political positions of the newspapers, and actions without organized publicity (whether by choice or by incapability of the subjects of the action) are more likely to be missing. Newspapers specializing in labor reporting reduce this problem somewhat but not diminish it fully, introducing their own selection patterns in the process. Earl et al. (2004) describe these issues as selection and description biases in collective-action research. To amend these biases, three newspapers specialized on labor reporting with national coverage, namely Evrensel, Sendika.org and BirGün, were utilized in an attempt to diversify the reporting. However, the usage of these three newspapers does not eliminate these biases fully since all three newspapers are publications of certain political entities with varying political agendas and their reach is still limited. Therefore, the resulting corpus from these sources cannot be claimed to be representative of all labor actions in Turkey.

One crucial bias on labor news reporting that should be noted here is the reporting of event endings. Events ending in victories are more likely to be reported on than defeats. This is partly because some actions dissolve without a final announcement without reaching their demands, thus there being not something to report on, and partly because newspapers reporting on labor actions more often than not are ideologically aligned with the side of labor against capital, thus being incentivised to not report on defeats which may affect the success of future labor actions. This creates a structural asymmetry in that the beginning of an action is far easier to observe than its conclusion, and the events not containing an end date should be handled with care

2.2 Adapting the LSC methodology

The extraction schema is adapted from the event-level recording practice of the Labor Studies Collective (LSC), which has been collecting detailed records of working class actions in Turkey for over a decade with a coding strategy developed by experts in the field. In this detailed recording practice, detailed categories of an event are recorded such as the workplace, sector, participating workers count, total worker count in the workplace, organizing trade union, employment status, action type, dates, location, reason, outcome, gender distribution of participants and much more; with detailed distinct recordings of each category. A detailed explanation of these can be found in one of many annual reports on Turkish working class activity published by the LSC. The pipeline here simplifies that richer scheme so that the variables can be recovered consistently from news text without human intervention.

The most difficult adaptation here is outcome coding. Labor actions are complicated, ever changing real life events that do not only consist of the initial demands and eventual result of the strike itself, but also all the events taking place throughout the lifespan of the action. Alongside additional demands and points of struggle arising during the action (such as the dismissal of workers as a result of the action, the struggle for those workers to be reappointed to their jobs, struggle against police brutality against the workers taking

action, the struggle against strikebreaking measures employed by the firm, the modification of demands by the workers according to the way the action is going and so on), unintended consequences that may be considered as successes can also become apparent throughout the course of the action. The emergence of a consolidated workplace committee which may ensure the success of future actions, the emergence of worker leaders who may be either employed by a specific union to organise different workplaces or stay at the current workplace and strengthen the prospects of a future action success, the confidence gained by workers throughout the action may all be considered as unintended successes of the strike. The opposite is also true, the heavy crushing of an action and the dismissal of leading workers may impede future action prospects throughout both the workplace and the region, both practically and through the motivational effects such defeats have on other workers. This would be an unintended failure of the action. Since these aspects of an action are virtually impossible to measure especially through text-as-event tracking methodologies, our pipeline will be focusing on only intended successes of actions events; that is, actions motivated by an initial demand which is observable. From this point on, any mention of “action success” should be understood as the success of actions regarding an explicit initial demand, unless stated otherwise.

In agreement with these concerns, the schema presented here codes outcomes only as FullGain, ZeroGain or Unknown (omitting the PartialGain coding utilized in the LSC framework). The coding FullGain requires explicit evidence of a victory, accepted demand, signed agreement, payment, reinstatement, wage gain, or comparable victory on the part of workers. Cases without such evidence which have not been reported on for 30 days (in an attempt to combat the (non)reporting bias on defeated strikes) and with explicit accounts of defeat are coded ZeroGain when their last article precedes 31 May 2025¹, and the cases which the model cannot confidently identify either category are coded as Unknown.

The action-reason category field forces the LLM to choose the event’s primary reason from five options: wage increase outside collective bargaining; collective bargaining agreement; unionization; dismissal; and privatization. Even though this restriction improves consistency, it compresses actions that contain more than one reason/demand into the primary reason the model can confidently detect; sacrificing the complexity of the event.

3 Evaluation Framework

Because the different stages of the pipeline serve different functions, the pipeline cannot be evaluated with a single end-to-end score. Detection is a retrieval problem, linking is a clustering problem, and extraction is a structured coding problem. Therefore, each stage is therefore evaluated separately using metrics appropriate to it.

There exist no universal performance thresholds determining whether an NLP system is sufficiently accurate for use in research. Appropriate operating points depend on the intended application, class prevalence, relative costs of false positives and false negatives, and availability of human review (Hernández-Orallo, Flach, and Ferri, 2012). Performance of the pipeline is thus interpreted in relation to the function of each stage instead of a generalized cutoff point.

The detection stage is designed to prioritize recall, for two reasons. First, even in

¹The date cutoff is implemented to overcome the right-censoring of continuing labor actions.

newspapers reporting on labor related news, the amount of articles regarding labor action pales in comparison to the total amount of articles. Second, a relevant article excluded at the detection stage cannot be recovered downstream, whereas false positives can still be removed in further stages through subsequent processing or manual review if one wishes to do so. Similar high recall strategies have been used in systematic-review screening, where the cost of excluding a relevant document is considered substantially greater than the cost of reviewing an irrelevant one (Wang et al., 2024). Our pipeline utilizes a minimum recall target of 0.90, an author-defined operational criterion relating to the cost of leaving out relevant articles. Precision, recall, F1, ROC-AUC, and average precision scores are reported together in light of this choice.

Linking is evaluated using pairwise precision, pairwise recall, pairwise F1, purity, and completeness. Pairwise precision measures whether articles grouped together concern the same event. Pairwise recall, on the other hand, measures whether articles concerning the same event are kept together. Purity measures whether predicted clusters avoid mixing different events. Completeness captures the fragmentation of true events across several clusters. Since aggregate metrics do not tell the whole story; cluster size, duration, source composition, and implausibly large clusters are also examined by the author. This framework follows event-coreference research in treating different forms of clustering error separately instead of reducing performance to one measure (Hürriyetoğlu et al., 2022).

Extraction is evaluated through manual category level validation of accuracy on the clusters. In this endeavour, no fixed accuracy boundary is used to claim the extraction of a category as reliable. Instead, each category is assessed with relation to its use for potential future research and ability to surmise the given categories through the pipeline. Aggregate precision, recall, or accuracy scores can conceal substantial differences between error types and extracted categories, making category specific error analysis necessary for document level information extraction (Das et al., 2022). A category such as worker count in the workplace is hardly reported on explicitly and may require further investigation by the researcher. The extraction results therefore should be interpreted as suggestions on the amount of human verification required, rather than as concrete measure of LLM success in event extraction. One thing to note here is that the outcome reporting “Unknown” is evaluated as affecting the accuracy negatively, since it shows an inability of the model to identify the outcome of an event.

4 Data

The final corpus contains 19,886 articles from the labor-oriented sections of Evrensel, BirGün, and Sendika.org for 2023–2025. The newspapers contribute 13,047, 4,967, and 1,872 articles respectively. This imbalance should be noted. The final model is subjected to far more Evrensel articles than the other sources and thus descriptive results should not be considered neutral estimates of Turkish labor conflict. One other imbalance to be noted is the discrepancy between positive and negative article classes, which was an issue touched upon before. Methods attempting to address this imbalance will be explained later.

The detection labels identify whether an article contains a relevant labor action or not. A separate event-ID annotation was coded to train and evaluate linking. The final linking evaluation contains 441 labeled articles grouped into 112 true clusters.

Standardizing measures on source columns, whitespace, dates, binary labels, and event

Table 1: Corpus and manually labeled detection data

Source	Corpus articles	Labeled	Positive	Negative
Evrensel (EVR)	13,047	853	241	612
BirGün (BIR)	4,967	306	94	212
Sendika.org (SES)	1,872	248	74	174
Total	19,886	1,407	409	998

ID’s are also implemented. This standardization measure is especially important for the employer extraction and title-token rules of the linking stage (which will be touched upon later), since even one damaged character can affect model performance.

5 Methods

5.1 Pipeline overview

The general outline of the pipeline is as follows: for the detection stage; articles from all three newspaper sources are loaded and standardized; labeled rows are used for out-of-fold detection evaluation; the final detector is trained on all labeled rows and is applied to the full corpus. For the linking stage, every positive row that is predicted by the detection model or manually labeled is proceeded into linking the linking stage; the rows in this stage are clustered through pairwise linking. Finally, clusters with at least two articles enter LLM event extraction.

5.2 Detection

Detection uses `dbmdz/bert-base-turkish-cased` sensitive to both the title and article content. Titles are kept alongside contents because Turkish labor reporting often names the action and/or workplace directly in the title. The general model is from the bidirectional transformer architecture introduced by Devlin et al. (2019). The best model was selected through a grid search algorithm comprising of 32 configurations and 160 total training runs when taking into account five-fold stratified cross-validation run in each configuration. The selected best configuration, `recall_weighted_512`, uses a 512-token maximum length, the `gelu_new` activation function, a learning rate of 2×10^{-5} , four epochs, 0.01 weight decay, 0.10 warmup, a linear scheduler, and a positive-class weight multiplier of 1.25 to account for the imbalance between positive and negative classes. Mixed precision is not implemented. Five-fold stratified cross-validation is then used to produce out-of-fold probabilities. The decision threshold is selected from these out-of-fold probabilities to meet a minimum recall target of 0.90, satisfying our reasoning for a high recall oriented model. The details regarding best model selection can be examined in Appendix A.

5.3 Event linking

All articles that are predicted by the detection model to be positive as well as every article manually labeled to be positive are passed onto the next stage as linking candidates. Sen-

tence representations are generated using the `paraphrase-multilingual-MiniLM-L12-v2` model, keeping in line with the general Sentence-BERT bi-encoder approach to efficient semantic comparison (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019). The choice of this model is justified by its efficiency rather than capability. The best model was selected through a grid search algorithm comprising of 66 configurations. The selected best configuration, `recall_union`, works by creating an edge between two articles within a 180-day window, a loose window in which an edge is created when at least one of three conditions holds: semantic similarity is at least 0.82; an extracted entity overlaps and similarity is at least 0.66; or within 14 days, at least one rare title token overlaps and similarity is at least 0.80. The details regarding best model selection can be examined in Appendix B.

Entity candidates are extracted through fairly conservative patterns such as ‘X workers,’ ‘X factory,’ municipality, university, and hospital names. These entity candidates are then normalized and filtered. Article pairs containing an edge are combined through union-find connected components². Even though this procedure of clustering through pairwise linking is computationally efficient, it contains a risk of producing transitive chaining. Suppose that article A is paired with article B and article B is paired with article C. Then, the model clusters articles A and C together, even in cases when taken separately an edge would never be constructed between articles A and C. This deficiency runs the risk of constructing mega clusters.

5.4 LLM extraction and manual validation

For the entity extraction stage, only clusters containing at least two articles are taken into account. This choice is motivated by resource availability, singleton events are important to examine but our current resources do not allow for the LLM assisted extraction of them due to their scale. The LLM `gpt-5.4-mini` is used to convert event clusters into structured event records. The responses are restricted to predefined variables and permitted category values by utilizing a Pydantic schema. The model is instructed to retrieve evidence based and conservative values, inferred only from the supplied articles and no other sources. The designated schema includes outcome, employer, sector, workplace worker count, organizing union presence, union authority status³, organization name, employment type, up to four action types, primary action reason, start and end dates, location, participant counts, evidence document IDs, outcome evidence, and a model confidence score. The last three are for manual examination. For details on category responses and reproducibility, see Appendix C.

The primary action reason category is restricted to five response values: wage increase (no collective bargaining agreement), collective bargaining agreement, unionization, dismissal, and privatization. When several action reasons are present in the event, the model is instructed to choose the primary reason of the event throughout the cluster.

Validity is measured through a manual examination of 70 randomly selected clusters, comprising of 32.1 percent of the 218 extracted clusters. Each available category receives 1 for correct, 0.5 for partially correct or substantively close, and 0 for incorrect. The employer category is excluded from the aggregate calculation and is used mainly as an

²The combination of deterministic rules and probabilistic or learned similarity aligns with established data matching practice (Fellegi & Sunter, 1969; Christen, 2012).

³In Turkish labor legislation, for a union to legally bargain for collective wage agreements and to go on strike it must have authority in both the sector and the workplace. For the sector, at least one percent of the workers in that sector must be members of that union. For the workplace, at least fifty percent of the workers in that workplace must be members of that union.

identification measure. Multiple action type responses, when present, are pooled into one single action type category. The examination results in 996 scored judgments. The cluster level accuracy score first averages the scored categories within each cluster and then takes the average across the 70 clusters; pooled category level accuracy takes the average of all judgments directly.

6 Results and Discussion

6.1 Detection stage

The detector performs at a satisfactory level. At the selected threshold of 0.9540, merged out-of-fold precision stands at 0.939, recall at 0.902, and F1 at 0.920. At the fold level, recall ranges from 0.902 to 0.963, and F1 from 0.897 to 0.946. The strength of the performance of the model is maintained across all three sources. BirGün has the highest recall at 0.957 and Evrensel has the lowest at 0.880, while still producing an F1 score of 0.900. This suggests that the model has adequately captured the specific linguistic properties of all three newspapers despite the imbalance regarding article counts.

Table 2: Out-of-fold detection performance at the selected threshold

Scope	Precision	Recall	F1	Accuracy	ROC-AUC
Merged OOF	0.939	0.902	0.920	0.955	0.984
BirGün	0.957	0.957	0.957	0.974	0.990
Evrensel	0.922	0.880	0.900	0.945	0.979
Sendika.org	0.971	0.905	0.937	0.964	0.994

When applied to the full corpus, the model predicts that 4,303 articles are positive. 4,305 articles enter the positive set after manual labels are preserved, corresponding to 21.6 percent of the corpus.

6.2 Linking stage

The selected best linking configuration looks reasonably balanced during grid selection. For 410 evaluation rows and 108 true clusters, the model managed to produce a pairwise precision score of 0.750, recall score of 0.519, and F1 score of 0.613. Re-evaluation in the final pipeline uses 441 labeled rows and 112 true clusters. On this expanded population, however, the pairwise precision score falls to 0.308, recall score to 0.184, and F1 score to 0.230. Purity remains reasonably high at 0.884, but completeness only reaches 0.503.

Table 3: Linking performance at selection and final re-evaluation

Evaluation	Pair prec.	Pair rec.	Pair F1	Purity	Completeness
Grid sel. (410 rows; 108 clusters)	0.750	0.519	0.613	0.915	0.700
Final labels (441 rows; 112 clusters)	0.308	0.184	0.230	0.884	0.503

The cluster diagnostics shed some light onto the reason for this failure. The 4,305 positive articles are assigned to 2,436 components: 2,218 singletons and 218 multi-article clusters. One component contains 1,275 articles and spans 1,090 days. This indicates a detrimental case of transitive chaining; locally similar articles are combined in a cluster that grows far beyond the actual event boundary. The discrepancy between the two scores is the result of the newly formed edges affecting the manually labeled clusters. Moreover, corrupting data parsing also seems to have contributed. None of the 499 Sendika.org linking candidates has a valid parsed date, and since the optimized linker compares only dated articles these are kept from the clustering stage even when they were manually labeled as clusters. Evrensel also contains 700 candidates without a properly parsed date. These articles are not taken as linking candidates and classified as singleton components makes the date parsing a direct cause of the low linking recall.

Table 4: Structure of the operational cluster output

Measure	Count	Share / note
Candidate articles	4,305	Detected or manually retained positives
Predicted clusters	2,436	Operational connected components
Singleton clusters	2,218	91.1% of clusters
Multi-article clusters	218	8.9%; used in LLM extraction
Largest cluster	1,275 articles	29.6% of candidates; 1,090-day span
Undated candidates	1,199	700 EVR and all 499 SES candidates
Sendika.org clusters	499	All singletons because dates are unparsed

6.3 Extraction stage

In the extraction stage, the LLM returns a structured row for all 218 multi-article clusters. Its mean self-reported confidence is 89.0 out of 100. The human audit produces a much lower average cluster-level accuracy of 0.661 and a pooled category level accuracy of 0.662.

The strongest categories are those that are generally stated directly in labor related news reporting: whether a union organizes the action, the employment type, the organization active in the action, location of the action, primary reason, and start date. The weighted accuracy score of the primary action reason category being 0.857 indicates that the restriction of a primary category across five values performs relatively well when including cases where a partially correct score indicates overlap between unionization and dismissal struggles. One thing that manual investigation reveals is that a sixth response value regarding wage delays should also be implemented.

The weakly performing categories are a reflection of both reporting structure, cluster quality and the structural limitations of news reporting. For example, worker counts mentioned in articles may refer to the total workers in the workplace, the number of workers taking a specific action or the number of workers dismissed because of said action. Articles are often not clear enough when designating what these numbers relate to. End dates are largely missing because unsuccessful actions are not covered and/or do not have a clear end date. The fact that the outcome category has a weighted accuracy score of only 0.574 indicates that the implemented date based ZeroGain rule is not sufficient.

Table 5: Manual validation of LLM extraction fields (70 clusters)

Field	N	Weighted accuracy	Strict accuracy
Organizing union presence	70	0.921	0.914
Employment type	70	0.914	0.900
Organizational actor	70	0.893	0.886
Province / district	69	0.877	0.841
Action reason	70	0.857	0.800
Action start date	70	0.829	0.829
Action type (slots pooled)	100	0.675	0.640
Union authority status	70	0.657	0.657
Sector	70	0.636	0.629
Outcome	68	0.574	0.529
Action end date	68	0.382	0.382
Participant count range	67	0.366	0.358
Participant count exact	67	0.358	0.343
Workplace worker count	67	0.269	0.269

6.4 Descriptive outputs

The full extracted database returns the outcomes of 147 clusters as ZeroGain, 47 as FullGain, and 24 as Unknown. It identifies the primary action reason as wage increase outside collective bargaining in 80, collective bargaining in 65, dismissal in 37, unionization in 34, and privatization in 2 clusters. A union organizing the action is present in 179 clusters.

Table 6: Selected distributions in the 218 extracted cluster records

Variable	Category	Count	Share
Outcome	ZeroGain	147	67.4%
Outcome	FullGain	47	21.6%
Outcome	Unknown	24	11.0%
Reason	Wage increase outside CB	80	36.7%
Reason	Collective bargaining (CB)	65	29.8%
Reason	Dismissal	37	17.0%
Reason	Unionization	34	15.6%
Reason	Privatization	2	0.9%
Organizing union presence	Present	179	82.1%

These extractions should not be treated as population averages. The extraction excludes 2,218 singletons, one of the extracted rows represents the mega cluster consisting of 1,275 articles, source coverage remains unbalanced, and the outcome accuracy score is

below what can be considered reliable. The high share of ZeroGain in particular is partially produced by the cutoff rule introduced and said rule should be justified scientifically. The most defensible observation is that among investigated clusters, the model can identify the primary action reason, employment type⁴, location, start dates, union presence and organizational actors with relatively high accuracy, while it cannot yet confidently measure outcomes, ending dates, action types, union authority status, sectors, total worker counts, and participation counts.

7 Limitations and Reproducibility

There are a variety of limitations which plague this pipeline.

First, the number of linking labels remains limited with respect to the diversity of employers, sectors, and events lasting for long periods of time due to taking different forms⁵. The final evaluation shows that the selected best model does not generalize as well as its initial selection score suggested. The issue with transitive merges and mega clusters should be addressed. Date normalization must also be repaired.

Second, event extraction is evaluated only for clusters containing multiple articles. This measure controls API costs but results in the exclusion of 91.1 percent of the predicted clusters. Furthermore, the manual validation measures category accuracy dependent on the clusters presented to the LLM. Given the shortcomings of the linking stage and the exclusion of singleton articles, the final database is far from representing actual labor action events in Turkey.

Third, even though the 0.5 score value implemented during category validation is useful for diversifying measurement and not limiting the evaluation to a binary outcome, this decision introduces a not well defined account of judgment into the accuracy score. Future validation should utilize a well written evaluation manual and more than one annotator to solve disagreements. Moreover, multiple annotators should be employed in every stage of the pipeline.

Fourth, a better performing linking model should be utilized instead of MiniLM for better performance.

The final computational environment of the pipeline used Python 3.12.13 on Google Colab with Linux 6.6.122+ (x86-64, glibc 2.35) and GCC 11.4.0. The principal libraries utilized were NumPy 2.0.2, pandas 2.2.2, PyTorch 2.11.0+cu128, scikit-learn 1.6.1, Transformers 5.10.1, Accelerate 1.13.0, Datasets 4.0.0, Sentence Transformers 5.5.1, openpyxl 3.1.5, xlrd 2.0.2, tqdm 4.67.3, OpenAI Python SDK 2.41.0, and Pydantic 2.12.3. GPU computation used CUDA 12.8 and cuDNN 9.19.0 on an NVIDIA A100-SXM4 GPU with 40 GB memory. The detection stage used the `dbmdz/bert-base-turkish-cased` model, the linking stage used `sentence-transformers/paraphrase-multilingual-MiniLM-L12-v2`, and event extraction was conducted through the OpenAI Responses API using `gpt-5.4-mini`. Google Drive was used for data storage and transfer, while Microsoft Excel files were used for inputs, outputs, and manual validation. OpenAI Codex, operating with GPT-5.5 at the High reasoning setting, was used for debugging.

⁴Despite the high accuracy score, the model critically fails in distinguishing between private sector employment and civil servants.

⁵An event may start out as simple workplace protests, a strike and then a struggle against dismissal, with different numbers of workers taking action against differing entities in each stage.

8 Conclusion

This paper conveys a three stage pipeline of automated labor event extraction for labor news with different levels of success. Detection stands as the strongest stage with the final BERTurk model meeting a 0.90 recall target while maintaining high precision and stable performance across folds and the three news sources. Linking is not yet strong enough to generate event level article clusters automatically. The selected configuration proves to be a reasonable starting point but the final pairwise F1 score of 0.230 indicates transitive linking and severe over merging. Even though the extraction stage performs better than the linking stage, accelerating at clearly reported categories such as action reason, union presence, employment type, location, and start date, its performance is far from satisfactory for action end dates, worker counts, and outcomes. All in all, the extraction stage should be implemented as an assisting tool for human coders rather than an automated extraction model.

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A Detection Grid Search and Best Model

The detection configurations were evaluated with five-fold stratified cross validation using the same labeled article set, title and content input, and random seed. The grid search considered the activation functions GELU, GELU-new, ReLU, and SiLU, together with hyperparameter profiles designed to test baseline training, stronger positive class weighting, recall oriented decision rules, 128, 256, and 512 token contexts, alternative learning rates and epoch counts, batch size and gradient accumulation, and stronger regularization. The final selection exercise comprised 32 configurations and 160 fold-level training runs. Each candidate was evaluated using precision, recall, F1, accuracy, ROC-AUC, and average precision at the conventional 0.50 threshold and at an out-of-fold threshold chosen under the minimum recall rule. Selection prioritized configurations that reached at least 0.90 recall and then retained the strongest precision and F1 balance.

Table 7: Selected detection configuration

Parameter	Selected value
Base model	dbmdz/bert-base-turkish-cased
Selected profile	recall_weighted_512
Activation	gelu_new
Maximum sequence length	512 tokens
Learning rate	2×10^{-5}
Training epochs	4
Weight decay	0.01
Warmup ratio	0.10
Learning-rate scheduler	Linear
Training batch size	8 on CUDA; 2 on CPU
Evaluation batch size	16 on CUDA; 4 on CPU
Gradient accumulation	1 step
Positive-class weight multiplier	1.25
Model-selection metric	Validation F1
Minimum recall target	0.90
Selected OOF threshold	0.928121
Mixed precision	Disabled
Cross-validation / seed	Five stratified folds / 42

B Linking Grid Search and Best Model

The linking search evaluated candidate selection and pairwise edge construction choices on articles with manual event identifiers. The final pipeline retained every predicted positive and every manually labeled positive. The downstream search compared multilingual Sentence Transformer representations and several edge construction profiles: semantic-only, semantic-or-title-and-time, precision-intersection, hybrid-union, and recall-union rules. Across these profiles, the search varied strict and loose cosine similarity thresholds, entity conditioned similarity floors, title conditioned similarity floors, 14, 30, 60, and 90 day principal windows, a 180 day loose window, title overlap and entity overlap requirements. Configurations were ranked principally by pairwise F1 scores, while pairwise precision and recall, purity, completeness, adjusted Rand index, normalized mutual information, cluster counts, and qualitative cluster diagnostics were used to identify over merging and fragmentation.

The selected `recall_union` rule creates an undirected edge when articles fall within the 180 day loose window and at least one of these three conditions holds: cosine similarity is at least 0.82; at least one extracted entity overlaps and similarity is at least 0.66; within 14 days, at least one rare title token overlaps and similarity is at least 0.80. The union find algorithm then converts the resulting edge graph into clusters. The stricter similarity threshold, entity similarity threshold, and temporal decay parameter are present in the saved configuration record but are not called by the optimized final edge construction function.

C Extraction Schema

The extraction stage applies the schema below to clusters containing at least two articles. Response values are generated only from the articles passed onto the cluster. The restricted categories must be responded to with one of the permitted values shown in Table 10; nullable categories may be returned as null when the evidence is absent. Metadata like `final_cluster_id`, `status`, and `error` is appended after validation and is not part of the model response. The entity category is also not taken into consideration for validation since it acts as a cluster identifier.

Table 9: Extraction categories

Category	Type	Definition
Outcome	Required categorical	Reported outcome of the event.
Entity	Nullable string	Employer or general campaign label.
Sector	Required categorical	Sector of employment defined by Turkish labor legislation.
Worker count in the workplace (exact)	Nullable integer	Exact total number of workers at the workplace.
Union presence	Required categorical	Whether a trade union organized the action.

Table 9 continued

Category	Type	Definition
Union authority	Required categorical	Collective bargaining authority of the union.
Organizational actor	Nullable string	Name of the organizing actor; “No actor” if none is present.
Employment type	Required categorical	Employment type defined by Turkish labor legislation.
Action type 1	Required categorical	Primary form of labor action.
Action type 2, 3, 4	Optional categorical	Additional action forms when explicitly supported by the cluster.
Action reason	Required categorical	Primary action reason for the event.
Action start date	Nullable string	Action start date.
Action end date	Nullable string	Action end date.
Province/district	Nullable string	Province and, when available, district.
Participant count (exact)	Nullable integer	Exact number of workers participating in the action.
Participant count (range)	Required categorical	A rough estimate of the number of workers participating in the action.
Evidence document ID’s	Required list of strings	The ID’s of articles supporting the extraction decisions.
Outcome evidence	Nullable string	Brief quotation regarding outcome decision.
Confidence	Required integer, 0–100	Model reported confidence score.

Table 10: Permitted values for closed categorical fields

Category	Permitted values
Outcome	FullGain; ZeroGain; Unknown

Table 10 continued

Category	Permitted values
Sector	Cement, soil and glass; Shipbuilding and marine transportation, warehouses and docks; Civil servant – local administration services; Invalid-Multiple; Civil servant – transportation services; Game, fish, agriculture and forestry; Trade, office, education and fine arts; Communication; Food industry; Health and social services; Oil, chemistry, rubber, plastic and medicine; Textiles, garments and leather; General works; Energy; Metal; Civil servant – health and public services; Civil servant – press, publishing and communication services; Civil servant – education, learning and science services; Civil servant – office, banking and insurance services; Unknown
Union presence	Yes; No; Unknown
Union authority	Union has authority; Union does not have authority but has membership; Civil servant union; Invalid-multiple; Unknown
Employment type	Private sector (Blue collar); Private sector (White collar); Private sector subcontractor; Public sector subcontractor; Public sector worker; Civil servant; Municipality subcontractor; Irregular, piecework, temporary, seasonal; Unknown
Action type (1–4)	De facto strike; Legal strike; Simple protest at the workplace; Permanent resistance; Unknown
Action reason	Wage increase (no collective bargaining agreement); Collective bargaining agreement; Unionization; Dismissal; Privatization
Participant count (range)	6–25; 26–50; 51–100; 101–250; 501–1000; 1001–2500; 2500+; Unknown

Table 8: Selected linking configuration

Parameter	Selected value
Embedding model	sentence-transformers/ paraphrase-multilingual-MiniLM-L12-v2
Edge profile	recall_union
Strict similarity threshold	0.90
Loose similarity threshold	0.82
Entity similarity threshold	0.78
Entity-floor similarity	0.66
Title-floor similarity	0.80
Main date window	14 days
Loose date window	180 days
Temporal-decay tau	25 days
Minimum rare-title overlap	1 token
Minimum entity overlap	1 entity
Grid-selection pair precision	0.7497
Grid-selection pair recall	0.5187
Grid-selection pair F1	0.6132
Grid-selection purity	0.9146
Grid-selection completeness	0.7000